

February 2022

Press Release

COVID-X at the 4YFN & Mobile World Congress

The COVID-X programme, supported by the European Commission under Horizon2020 Programme, is very happy to announce its presence at the [4yfn & the Mobile World Congress](#) (28.01-03.03).

COVID-X funds [EU tech Companies](#) and [Healthcare Providers](#) to boost data-driven solutions with the power to overcome challenges in Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Follow-up and fight against the pandemic. In addition to the direct funding, COVID-X provides top-ranked solutions access to a tailored 10 month long acceleration programme.

Two Open Calls already took place with a final result of 15 solutions funded for OC1 and 14 selected solutions for funding within OC2.

[Four OC1 COVID-X Game Changers will be in Barcelona](#). Healthcare providers interested in their solutions and their outcomes can find them at the event (see the booth numbers in the links on the names):

[Covid@Home](#) ([Be Well innovations](#)): A tool for home care monitoring leading to a better understanding of distributing the burden between hospital care and home care.

[Healthentia - Care4Covid](#) ([Innovation SPRINT](#)): Healthentia Care4COVID helps healthcare providers to improve their COVID-19 resilience by managing COVID-19 related symptoms of patients and health workers from remote and providing targeted support and care guidelines to them.

[Segtnan](#) ([Synaptic](#)): Innovative AI software enabling individualised group testing at any laboratory.

[DDRehab](#) ([Ab.Acus](#)): A remote physical and cognitive rehabilitation system of long-lasting coronavirus patients through smartphone use and merging different clinical data sets to set up personalised rehabilitation plans.

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Some organisations will attend the event from the consortium side: [FGS](#), [SERMAS](#), [Bosonit](#), [Civitta](#) & [AUSTRALO](#), [netcompany-intrasoft](#), [UPM](#) and [Eight Bells](#), will have a booth with information about the final release of the sandbox.

If you are a healthcare provider willing to meet the solutions, please contact Blanca Arregui (blanca@australo.org) to organise a meeting with them.

COVID-X involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from 7 different countries:

CIVITTA

netcompany
intrasoft

HUMANITAS
RESEARCH HOSPITAL

For more information

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